

PROXIMATE, MINERAL, PHYTOCHEMICAL AND AMINO ACID COMPOSITION OF
Ocimum gratissimum and *Ocimum sanctum* LEAFMEALS AS POTENTIAL FEED ADDITIVES IN
MONOGASTRIC NUTRITION

P.C.N. Alikwe¹, E.I. Ohimain^{2*}, S.M. Omotosho³, and O.O. Afolabi⁴

¹Animal Science Department, ²Veterinary Microbiology Research Unit, Biological Sciences Department, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, PMB 071 Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria; *Corresponding author:

³SMO Laboratory Services 5 Joyce B Shopping Complex Ring Road Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

⁴Biochemistry Laboratory IAR&T, Moore Plantation, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Two species of the plants of genus *Ocimum* were sampled in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The leaves were cleaned, dried, milled and analyzed for minerals, essential amino acids and phytochemicals. Proximate analysis was also carried out. The results were subjected to statistical analysis using independent t-test to compare the properties of both plant species. The results show that *O. gratissimum* consists of 16.27±0.19% Crude Protein, 4.58±0.18% Crude Fat, 17.22±0.17% Crude Fibre, 12.33±0.54% Total Ash, 36.12±0.37% NFE, 86.52±0.33% Dry Matter, 13.48±0.33% Moisture Content and Gross Energy of 3.75±0.05 Kcal/kg. These values are not significantly different from *O. sanctum*. The concentration of minerals in *O. gratissimum* are as follows; Na (0.76±0.02mg/100g), Ca (0.52±0.01mg/100g), P (0.34±0.01 mg/100g), K (1.34±0.05 mg/100g), Mn (31.30±0.23mg/kg), Cu (13.71±0.17mg/Kg), Zn (27.50±0.36mg/kg), Mg (0.35±0.02mg/kg), and Fe (713.33±2.60mg/kg). Heavy metal composition of *O. gratissimum* are as follows; Pb (1.70±0.09mg/kg), Cd (0.05±0.01 mg/kg), Cr (1.55±0.06 mg/kg) and Ni (0.86±0.03 mg/kg). The concentration of essential amino acids in *O. gratissimum* are as follows; Methionine (0.85±0.04%), Lysine (1.13±0.03%), Alanine (0.97±0.03%), Cystine (0.27±0.01%) and Tryptophan (0.71±0.03%). Phytochemical content of *O. gratissimum* are as follows; Alkaloid (0.84±0.01%), Saponin (0.62±0.01%), Phenol (0.19±0.01%) and Glycoside (0.10±0.00%). With these properties, we therefore conclude that the leaf meal of the plant *Ocimum* is suitable as feed additive for monogastric nutrition.

KEY WORDS: Animal nutrition, essential amino acids, feed additives, leafy meal, minerals, phytochemicals

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Corresponding Author: ehimain@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Among the plants known for their medicinal value, the plants of genus *Ocimum* belonging to family Labiatae are very important for their therapeutic potentials. *Ocimum sanctum* L. (Labiatae) is a strongly scented small annual herb, up to 18 inches tall, grows into a low bush and is commonly known as holy basil, Tulsi or Tulasi (Mahmood *et al.*, 2008). While *Ocimum gratissimum* known as (Ram Tulsi), the local names are Efinrin, Efinrin aaja, Erumaba (Yoruba), Daidoyatagida (Hausa), Esewon (Akoko-Edo, Edo State), Nehonwu, Nchanwu (Igbo), Erushin (Ika, Delta State) and Menthesauvage (French). It is traditionally used to relieve pains and also used in the treatment of rheumatism, diarrhea, high fever, convulsions, diabetes, eczema, piles and as a repellent (Chitwood, 2003, Hotlets *et al.*, 2003). The decoction of the stem is inhaled for the treatment of catarrh and bronchitis (Gills, 1992). Both are examples of known important species of genus *Ocimum* which grow in different parts of the world and are known to have medicinal properties (Satyavati *et al.*, 1976; Gupta *et al.*, 2002; Nagarajan *et al.*, 1987; Sen, 1993; Prakash and Gupta, 2005). *Ocimum sanctum* L. is commonly

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cultivated in gardens in Indian subcontinent. *Ocimum sanctum* L. contains Vitamin C, and minerals like calcium, zinc and iron (Anbarasu and Vijayalakshmi, 2007), as well as chlorophyll and many other phytonutrients. It enhances efficient digestion, absorption and use of nutrients from food and other herbs. This plant contain protein: 4.2 g, fat: 0.5 g, carbohydrate: 2.3 g, calcium: 25 mg, phosphorus: 287 mg, iron: 15.1 mg and edible portion 25 mg; Vitamin C per 100 g (Pattanayak *et al.*, 2010). The medicinal value of these plants lies in bioactive phytochemical constituents that produce definite physiological action on the human (and animal) body (Akinmoladun *et al.*, 2007). The chemical composition of *Ocimum sanctum* L. is highly complex, containing many nutrients and other biologically active compounds, the proportions of which may vary considerably between varieties and even among plants within the same field. The medicinal plants are rich in secondary metabolites (which are potential sources of drugs) and essential oils of therapeutic importance. The important advantages claimed for therapeutic uses of medicinal plants in various ailments are their safety besides being economical, effective and their easy availability (Siddiqui, 1993). *Ocimum sanctum* L. or *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (Pattanayak *et al.*, 2010) has been well documented for its therapeutic potentials and described as antiasthmatic and antikaphic drugs. Furthermore, the quantity of many of these constituents are significantly affected by differing growing, harvesting, processing and storage conditions that are not yet well understood (Pattanayak *et al.*, 2010). The nutritional and pharmacological properties of the whole herb in its natural form, as it has been traditionally used, result from synergistic interactions of many different active phytochemicals. Hence the need to investigate the phytochemicals, minerals and amino acid content of *Ocimum sanctum* and *O. gratissimum* growing luxuriantly in Bayelsa State for possible usage as a feed additive and veterinary herbal drug in monogastric nutrition and management

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ocimum gratissimum and *O. sanctum* leaves were collected from a garden at Agudama located in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria, cleaned and spread on the already cleaned laboratory table for 5 days in the Animal Science Laboratory, Niger Delta University. Dried leaves were milled and a portion (50 g) of the powdered samples was processed for various parameters according to the following procedures: The proximate analyses of the plants leaf were determined by the method described by AOAC (1990). Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS), bulk scientific model AVG 210 was used for elemental composition and appropriate working standard solution was prepared for each element and calibration curves were obtained for concentration versus absorbance. Total phenolics were determined by method described by Mole and Waterman (1987), Saponins by the spectrophotometric method of Brunner as described by Akinmutimi and Okwu (2006), Alkaloids by gravimetric method of Harbone (Harbone, 1998), Tannins was determined by method of Maga as described by Akinmutimi and Okwu (2006) and Phytate by Lucas and Markakas method as described by Akinmutimi and Okwu (2006). IBM-SPSS version 20 was used for statistical analysis. All data were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard error.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of proximate analysis (in %) of *O. gratissimum*, and *O sanctum* leafmeal are shown in Table 1. The plants contained high amount of carbohydrates content which were 36.20% and 36.91% respectively. These results are lower to that reported for *A. sativum* (57.28) (Hussain *et al.*, 2009) and the value reported for *P. fistulosus* (62.39) (Hussain *et al.*, 2009), but are higher than that of *Senna obtusifolia* (23.70%) and similar to *Amaranthus incurvatus* (39.05%) (Faruq *et al.*, 2002) Carbohydrate constitutes a major class of naturally occurring organic compounds which are essential for the maintenance of life in plant and animals and also provide raw materials for many industries (Ebun-Oluwa and Alade, 2007). The plant is a good source of carbohydrate when consumed because it meets the Recommended Dietary Allowance (RDA) values (FND, 2002). The crude protein content of *O. gratissimum*, *O. sanctum* were 16.28% and 16.38% respectively. These are higher than the protein content of *Telfaria occidentalis* (7.00%) and *Momordica balsania* L. (11.29%) (Isong and Idong, 1997), but however lower than those of *Piper guineensis* (29.78%) and *Talinum triangulare* (31.00%) (Akindahunsi and Salawu, 2005). However, it compared favourably with the value reported for *A. viridus* (16.41%) (Pandey *et al.*, 2006). The plants are considered as a good source of protein because it provides more than 12% of calorific value from protein (Pearson, 1976).

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The ash content of *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum* leafmeals were 12.26% and 11.38% which is lower than the values reported for the leaves of *A. viridus* 22.84% (Pandey *et al.*, 2006), but similar to *Ipomea batatas* with 11.10% and *Moringa deifera* with 15.09% (Antia *et al.*, 2006). They are however higher than that of *A. sativum* with 4.84 (Hussain *et al.*, 2009). The ash content is a reflection of the amount of mineral elements present in the samples; therefore, the plants contained a good amount of minerals.

The moisture content values for the leaves of *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum* (13.48% and 13.46%), were relatively low, therefore it could hinder the growth of microorganisms and the life span of the stored samples would be high. This is good for the long preservation and will prevent early spoilage. The moisture content of the plant is low when compared to that of *Xylophia aethiopia* (16.04%) (Abolaji *et al.*, 2007) but similar to *Acalypha hispida* (11.91%) Iniaqhe *et al.* (2009).

The values of the crude fat for the leaves of *O. garanissimu* and *O. sanctum* were 4.57% and 4.33% which were moderate in amount when compared to those of *Talinum triangulare* (5.09%), similar to that of *Amarantus hybridus* (4.80%) (Akindahunsi and Salawu 2005) and higher than *Gnetum africanum* (3.15%) (Abolaji *et al.*, 2007). Dietary fat increases the palatability of food by absorbing and retaining flavour (Antia *et al.*, 2006) A diet providing 1.20% of its caloric of energy as fat is said to be deficient for human being as excess fat consumption is implicated in certain cardiovascular disorders (Antia *et al.*, 2006)

The crude fibre values for the leaves of *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum* were 17.21% and 17.54% which are high when compared to that of *A. esculentus* with 14.71%, *M. charantia* with 16.62% (Hussain *et al.*, 2009) but much lower to *P. thonningii* with 35.03% (Ene-Obong and Carnovale, 1992). The values obtained in this study are also higher than that of *Gnetum africanum* (4.60%), *M. ureans* (4.00%) and *Parinari polyandra* (4.90%) (Ekpo, 2007). The plants are good source of crude fibre when consumed because adequate intake of dietary fibre helps in digestion and defecation. It can as well lower the serum cholesterol level, heart disease, hypertension, constipation, diabetes and breast cancer (Ishida *et al.*, 2000).

The mineral composition (in mg/100g) of *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum* leafmeal were shown in Table 2a. The values of sodium in the plants varied from 0.69 (*O. sanctum*) to 0.76 (*O. gratissimum*) while that of potassium varied from 1.41 (*O. sanctum*) to 1.34 (*O. gratissimum*). The ratio of sodium to potassium is less than 1 (0.5/0.56); therefore consumption of the plants would reduce high blood pressure disease because Na:K is less than one as recommended by FND (2002) The value of calcium and phosphorous in the leafmeal of *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum* varied from 0.34/0.25 to 0.52/0.44 Calcium and phosphorous are associated with each other for growth and maintenance of bones, teeth and muscles (Okaka *et al.*, 2006). The calcium level in the leafmeals studied compared favourably with the values reported in some green leafy vegetables consumed in Nigeria and some wild edible leaves grown in Eastern Anatolia, Turkey (Ladan *et al.*, 1996). Therefore, *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum* are sources of calcium and phosphorous which aids intestinal absorption (Guil – Guerrero *et al.*, 1998). Magnesium content of *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum* varied from 0.35 to 0.41mg/kg. Magnesium is a component of chlorophyll and it is important in calcium metabolism in bones (Ishida *et al.*, 2000). Zinc content of *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum* varied from 27.50 to 44.3 mg/kg, which are lower than the values (70.10 mg/kg) recorded for *Pilostigma thioningi* (Elegbede, 1998). Zinc is involved in normal functioning of immune system (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2001) and is associated with protein metabolism. The leafmeals are a good source of zinc because it is far above 6.23 recommended by RDA (Borgert *et al.*, 1975). Iron content of *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum* varied from 689 to 713 mg/kg. These values are higher compared with the values reported for *Ipomea batata* 16.00 mg/100g i.e. 160 mg/kg (Antia *et al.*, 2006) and compared fairly to the values of other green leafy vegetables as reported by Ibrahim *et al.* (2001). Iron is an essential trace element for haemoglobin formation, normal functioning of central nervous system and in the oxidation of carbohydrates, protein and fats (Adeleye and Otokiti, 1999). This perhaps justifies the already locally established function of the plant in the regulation of haemoglobin level. The values of manganese in the leaves of *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum* varied from 31.30 to 36.50mg/kg. Heavy metals such as Lead, Cadmium, Chromium and Nickel are present in various nontoxic levels in both species of *Ocimum*.

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The Amino Acid constituent of *O. gratissimum* indicated the presence of Methionine (0.85mg/100g), Lysine (1.13mg/100g), Alanine (0.97mg/100g), Cysteine (0.27mg/100g) and Tryptophan (0.62mg/100g). The phytochemicals found in both plants were Saponins 0.623/0.631mg/100g, Phenols 0.194/0.179mg/100g and Alkaloids:0.856/0.867mg/100g while the glycoside was 0.102/0.097mg/100g. The phytochemical component studied revealed that *O.gratissimum* and *O. sanctum* have substantial amount of Saponins, Phenols, Alkaloids, and Glycoside which are known to act as the pharmaceutical components of the plants. According to Kawo *et al.* (2009), phytochemical components are responsible for both pharmacological and toxic activities in plants. These metabolites are said to be useful to a plant itself but can be toxic to animals including man. These are known to exhibit medicinal activity as well as physiological activity (Sofowora, 1993). Various studies have shown that Saponins although non-toxic can generate adverse physiological responses in animals that consume them in large quantities. They exhibit cytotoxic effect and growth inhibition against a variety of cell making them to have anti-inflammatory and anticancer properties. They also show tumour inhibiting activity on animals (Akindahunsi and Salawu, 2005). From the above results, these leaves may serve as a constituent of livestock/human diet supplying the body with minerals, protein and energy. The presence of secondary plant products in the leaves of *Ocimum* species make them biologically important e.g. saponins and phenols contributes to its medicinal value thus they can be potential sources of useful drugs. The stem and leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* L. contain a variety of constituents that may have biological activity, including saponins, flavonoids, triterpenoids and tannins (Jaggi *et al.*, 2003) In previous study, it has been shown that, organic extracts of *Ocimum sanctum* L. show wide zones of inhibition against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococci* sp., *Shigella* sp., *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Enterobacteria* sp. (Rahman *et al.*, 2010). Other researchers showed it is also potent against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococci* sp., *Salmonella typhi*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus*, *Candida albicans*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and *Micrococcus pyogenes* when studied by agar diffusion method (Mishra and Mishra, 2011; Farivar *et al.*, 2006). Alcoholic extract showed wider zone for *Vibrio cholera* (Geeta *et al.*, 2001). It has one tenth anti-tubercular potency of streptomycin and one-fourth that of isoniazid. Higher content of linoleic acid in *Ocimum sanctum* L. fixed oil could contribute towards its antibacterial activity. The oil show good antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus pumius* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, where *S. aureus* was the most sensitive organism (Singh *et al.*, 2005). Extract of *Ocimum sanctum* L. caused inhibition of *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* clinical isolates and WHO organization strains. This activity is comparable to penicillin and ciprofloxacin (Shokeen *et al.*, 2005).

CONCLUSION

Plants have contributed immensely to the medical/veterinary and nutritional field. It has been the source of most drugs such as antibiotics (additives) used for combating infections. The two plants used in this study were found to contain the important constituent needed to combat various kinds of infection in monogastric animals and human beings. *Ocimum sanctum* L. is known as a general vitalizer and increases physical endurance but it do not contains caffeine or other stimulants.

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Table 1: Proximate Analysis of *Ocimum gratissimum* and *Ocimum sanctum*

	Crude Protein, %	Crude Fat, %	Crude Fibre, %	Total Ash, %	NFE, %	Dry Matter, %	Moisture Content, %	Gross. Energy (Kcal/kg)
<i>O. gratissimum</i>	16.27±0.19	4.58±0.18	17.22±0.17	12.33±0.54	36.12±0.37	86.52±0.33	13.48±0.33	3.75±0.05
<i>O. sanctum</i>	16.38±0.10	4.33±0.07	17.54±0.31	11.38±0.14	36.91±0.72	86.54±0.11	13.46±0.11	3.88±0.18
T value*	-0.519 ^{NS}	1.26 ^{NS}	-0.914 ^{NS}	1.701 ^{NS}	-0.966 ^{NS}	-0.057 ^{NS}	0.057 ^{NS}	-0.72 ^{NS}

*n = 3, df = 4, S = significant difference (p<0.05), NS =non significant (p>0.05) (two tailed)

Table 2a: Mineral Analysis of *Ocimum gratissimum* and *Ocimum santum*

	Na mg/100g	Ca mg/100g	P mg/100g	K mg/100g	Mn mg/Kg	Cu mg/Kg	Zn mg/Kg	Mg mg/Kg	Fe mg/Kg
<i>O. gratissimum</i>	0.76±0.02	0.52±0.01	0.34±0.01	1.34±0.05	31.30±0.23	13.71±0.17	27.50±0.36	0.35±0.02	713.33±2.60
<i>O. sanctum</i>	0.69±0.02	0.44±0.02	0.25±0.01	1.41±0.05	36.37±0.25	14.20±0.23	44.36±0.27	0.41±0.02	689.00±3.46
T value*	2.169 ^{NS}	3.054 ^S	5.295 ^S	-1.072 ^{NS}	-15.067 ^S	-1.706 ^{NS}	-37.598 ^S	-2.078 ^{NS}	5.615 ^S

*n = 3, df = 4, S = significant difference (p<0.05), NS =non significant (p>0.05) (two tailed)

Table 2b: Heavy metal analysis of *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum*

	Pb, mg/kg	Cd, mg/kg	Cr, mg/kg	Ni, mg/kg
<i>O. gratissimum</i>	1.70±0.09	0.05±0.01	1.55±0.06	0.86±0.03
<i>O. sanctum</i>	2.10±0.05	0.06±0.01	2.55±0.03	1.29±0.01
T value*	-4.075 ^S	-1.225 ^{NS}	-14.852 ^S	-14.981 ^S

*n = 3, df = 4, S = significant difference (p<0.05), NS =non significant (p>0.05) (two tailed)

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Table 3: Essential Amino acid Analysis of *Ocimum gratissimum* and *Ocimum sanctum*

	Methionine, %	Lysine, %	Alanine, %	Cystine, %	Tryptophan, %
<i>O. gratissimum</i>	0.85±0.04	1.13±0.03	0.97±0.03	0.27±0.01	0.63±0.02
<i>O. sanctum</i>	1.11±0.02	2.27±0.02	1.29±0.01	0.33±0.02	0.71±0.03
T value*	-6.205 ^S	-30.623 ^S	-10.292 ^S	-2.324 ^{NS}	-2.245 ^{NS}

*n = 3, df = 4, S = significant difference (p<0.05), NS =non significant (p>0.05) (two tailed)

Table 4: Quantitative Phytochemical Analysis of *O. gratissimum* and *O. sanctum*

	Alkaloid, %	Saponin, %	Phenol, %	Glycoside, %
<i>O. gratissimum</i>	0.84±0.01	0.62±0.01	0.19±0.01	0.10±0.00
<i>O. sanctum</i>	0.87±0.00	0.63±0.01	0.18±0.00	0.10±0.00
T value*	-1.959 ^{NS}	-0.521 ^{NS}	1.993 ^{NS}	1.021 ^{NS}

*n = 3, df = 4, S = significant difference (p<0.05), NS =non significant (p>0.05) (two tailed)